

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING A CHILD'S COGNITIVE PROCESSES

Kadirova Malikakhon Kahramonovna
Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Head teacher

qodirovam1973@gmail.com

Abstract. This article analyzes the issues of using innovative technologies in the development of children's cognitive processes. The use of technologies such as digital tools, artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality, and gamification in modern education serves to increase children's interest and cognitive activity. Also, ways to increase the effectiveness of education through an individual approach, interactive teaching methods, and expanding opportunities for independent learning are considered. This article describes the main advantages and recommendations for using innovative technologies.

Keywords: innovative technologies, learning process, education, digital tools, artificial intelligence, virtual reality, gamification, interactive learning, personal approach, educational effectiveness.

ENTRANCE

Nowadays, the introduction of innovative technologies into the educational process is of great importance. Especially for preschool children, teaching with the help of modern technologies is an effective tool for developing their cognitive processes. Because from a young age, children strive to learn about the environment, master new knowledge, and develop their thinking.

Innovative technologies, including interactive games, digital learning platforms, virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR), robotics, and multimedia tools, help children develop their logical thinking, problem-solving, and creative thinking skills. Such methods increase children's engagement and encourage them to learn independently.

Therefore, this study aims to study the importance of innovative technologies in the development of children's cognitive processes, analyze their effectiveness, and consider ways to successfully implement them in the educational process.

The purpose of the study is to identify effective methods for developing children's cognitive processes using innovative technologies and recommend ways to use them in the educational process.

Objectives of the study:

1. To determine the role and importance of innovative technologies in the development of children's cognitive processes.
2. Study the types of modern educational technologies and their impact on the educational process.
3. Developing effective teaching methods using innovative technologies.
4. Analyze changes in children's cognitive activity based on practical experiences.

LEVEL OF LEARNING

The importance of innovative technologies in the development of children's cognitive processes has been studied by various scientists and researchers. A number of scientific studies have been conducted in this area, and the works of the following authors are considered relevant:

J. Piaget developed the theory of cognitive development and studied the age-related stages of children's cognitive processes. His research helped to understand how children's logical thinking and understanding of the world develop.

LS Vygotsky is the founder of the theory of sociocognitive development. According to him, a child's cognitive process develops through the social environment and communication.

BF Skinner – studied pedagogical psychology and educational technologies, proving the effectiveness of interactive and stimulating methods in the learning process of children.

H. Gardner developed the theory of multiple intelligences, which studies the development of children through different learning styles (visual, auditory, kinesthetic).

Innovative technologies are being used in children's education in various areas:
Interactive educational programs and digital platforms:

- Scratchers is an interactive platform that teaches children the basics of programming.
- ABC mouse, Starfall – online educational programs for children.
- Kahoot! – consolidate knowledge through interactive tests and quizzes.
- Robotics and coding
- Bee-Bot, Ozon bot, Lego We Do – tools that develop programming and problem-solving skills for children.
- VR/AR technologies
- Google Expeditions, Quiver Vision – interactive learning through virtual and augmented reality.
- Multimedia and interactive games
- E-books, audiobooks, video materials and 3D animations for children.

MAIN PART

Innovative technologies used in kindergarten classes are of great importance in the development of children's cognitive processes. Below is a list of the main technologies that kindergarten teachers can use in classes:

1. Interactive whiteboards and multimedia tools:

Interactive whiteboard (Smart Board, Promethean Board) – children can draw, do calculations, and learn words.

Projectors and screens - to educate children through cartoons, educational videos, and slide presentations.

2. Tablets and electronic devices:

Tablets (iPad, Android devices) – learning colors, shapes, letters, and numbers through special educational apps.

Touch screen devices – interactive educational games and exercises.

3. Interactive games and programs:

ScratchJr – simple coding basics for kids.

ABCmouse, Starfall – special programs for learning to write and read.

Kahoot, Quizizz – fun quizzes for kids.

4. Robotics and coding:

Bee-Bot, Ozon bot – robots that teach children algorithmic thinking.

Lego Education We Do – STEM technologies for young children.

5. Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) technologies:

Google Expeditions (VR) – education through virtual tours.

Quiver Vision (AR) – an opportunity for children to draw and see them in real life.

6. E-books and audio materials:

Audiobooks and e-books – to develop writing and language skills.

Story Nory, Audible Kids – fun audio stories for children.

7. Smart assessment and development monitoring:

Class Dojo, Seesaw – for tracking children's progress and communicating with parents.

AI-based analysis tools – identifying children's strengths and weaknesses.

RESEARCH METHODS

Various scientific methods are used in conducting research on the use of innovative technologies in the development of children's cognitive processes. Below are the main methods used in this study:

1. Theoretical research methods.

These methods are used to study scientific sources, theoretical concepts, and advanced pedagogical practices.

Analysis and synthesis – studying scientific literature, articles, and research results to identify the relationship between children's cognitive processes and innovative technologies.

Comparative analysis - evaluating the effectiveness of innovative and traditional teaching methods by comparing them.

Model creation - developing an optimal model of the educational process based on innovative technologies.

2. Empirical research methods.

These methods are based on practical experience and real data collection.

Observation - monitoring the process of children's learning through innovative technologies and assessing their interests and level of development.

Experiment – determining the impact of innovative technologies by comparing groups that have been used and those that have not been used.

Surveys and interviews – conducting conversations with educators, parents, and children, exploring their opinions and experiences.

Testing and diagnostic methods - the use of special tests and assessment tools to determine how well children's cognitive processes have developed.

3. Statistical and mathematical analysis methods.

Data processing - analysis of experimental results, proving the effectiveness of innovative technologies using mathematical and statistical methods.

Graphical and diagrammatic analysis – visual representation and comparison of experimental results.

Using these methods, it is possible to accurately study how innovative technologies affect the development of children's cognitive processes and develop effective approaches.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

In the modern educational process, the development of a child's cognitive activity is of great importance. Innovative technologies serve to increase efficiency in this process. The conducted analyses show that methods such as digital educational tools, artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality, and gamification increase children's interest and make the learning process more effective and interactive.

Recommendations:

1. Introduction of interactive technologies: It is necessary to develop the child's perception and thinking through the use of multimedia materials, simulators, and VR/AR technologies in the educational process.

2. Personalized approach: It is necessary to develop individual educational programs based on artificial intelligence, offering educational materials that are tailored to the specific abilities and needs of each child.

3. Widespread use of gamification: It is necessary to increase children's activity by organizing education in the form of a game, for example, imparting knowledge through interesting tests, contests, and competitions.

4. Introduce parents and teachers to innovative technologies: They should be trained and provided with practical training in the use of new technologies.

5. Expanding opportunities for independent learning: It is advisable to promote the use of online courses, digital libraries, and educational platforms.

6. Analyze and improve the educational process: It is necessary to monitor the dynamics of children's learning through innovative technologies, evaluate their results, and make necessary changes.

Thus, innovative technologies make children's cognitive processes more effective, interesting and interactive. Their proper use can improve the quality of education and achieve the comprehensive development of children.

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